

Wearing Face Mask for COVID-19 Prevention: A timely example of Prevention Paradox

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Abstract

According to Thompson, a "prevention paradox" is characterized as a prevention that has numerous benefits for the entire population but may not be as useful to each individual as it is to the entire community. We are currently dealing with COVID-19, one of the most mysterious emerging viruses in history, which can be transmitted from one person to another mostly through breathing. We will all be infected very quickly if we do not follow certain recommendations, such as wearing a face mask. millions of individuals should put on face masks to help a small percentage of the population avoid death.

Keywords: Prevention Paradox, COVID-19, Face Mask, Pandemic, Epidemiology

Dear Editor

We're going to discuss about the "Prevention Paradox", which is an interesting but not well-known paradox. To become familiar with it, we must first explain its meaning. According to Thompson, a "prevention paradox" is characterized as a prevention that has numerous benefits for the entire population but may not be as useful to each individual as it is to the entire community (1). This is due to the tiny number of persons under danger. Some health issues, such as alcohol-related injuries and road safety, have already been addressed with this technique (2,3). Fastening a car safety belt, for example, has been shown to reduce the number of deaths caused by traffic accidents (4). Then it became legal, and now all drivers and passengers are required to wear seat belts in order to limit the number of deaths in the event of a traffic accident. To put it another way, everyone in

their vehicle must use seat belts to save the lives of a few people.

We are currently dealing with COVID-19, one of the most mysterious emerging viruses in history, which can be transmitted from one person to another mostly through breathing (5). We will all be infected very quickly if we do not follow certain recommendations, such as wearing a face mask. Although there is a fair probability that the person who is infected will not develop an illness and will recover after a short period of time, the virus could be passed to persons in the high-risk group, infecting them and placing them in grave danger as a result. As a result, practically all scientists have recommended that everyone use face masks to prevent the virus from spreading (6,7).

To be honest, we recognize that this problem will persist until all countries achieve herd immunity through vaccination. As a result, millions of

individuals should put on face masks to help a small percentage of the population avoid death. It may be tedious, difficult, or even irritating, but it is one of the most efficient strategies to stop COVID-19 from spreading. Since we appear to have no other option, it is highly recommended that we all wear face masks.

Keywords: Prevention Paradox, COVID-19, Face Mask, Pandemic, Epidemiology

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